

OPIOID ADDICTION DEATHS IN THE UNITED STATES: SOCIOECONOMIC IMPLICATIONS

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11093894>

Abstract: Researchers from all across the world have closely examined opioid addiction deaths that result from drug consumption, including overdoses and addiction instances in industrialized economies. However, no recent study has included economic growth as a socioeconomic factor contributing to opioid addiction death in the United States. To close this knowledge gap, this study examines the relationship between socioeconomic variables such as unemployment and poverty and the level of education attained by residents who hold bachelor's or higher degrees, as well as the US economy's growth. The US Census Bureau and the NCDAS's 2023 record provided cross-sectional data on opioid addiction mortality and socioeconomic characteristics in 51 US states. The results of the OLS regression model indicate a significant correlation between socioeconomic characteristics, such as economic growth, and the number of opioid addiction deaths. According to FMOLS, while traditional socioeconomic characteristics like unemployment and educational attainment play a significant role in the high number of opioid addiction deaths in the US, integrated economic growth dramatically lowers the number of opioid addiction deaths. Therefore, socioeconomic implications have both positive and negative effects on the prevalence of opioid addiction deaths. As a result, the US Food and Drug Administration should continuously raise awareness among the unemployed and educated addict population and provide funding for sustainable economic growth and development. These actions will eventually reduce the number of opioid addiction deaths in the United States.

Keywords: Opioid addiction deaths, Socioeconomic implications, FMOLS, OLS Regression

Introduction

The United States is currently facing a persistent epidemic of drug overdoses. The dynamics of the crisis are undergoing rapid transformation. The crisis has been divided into three main waves. In the late 1990s, there was a significant surge in overdoses related to prescription opioids. Mortality rates due to heroin overdoses began to increase in 2010. According to Scholl et al. (2019), there has been a significant rise in fatal overdoses related to synthetic opioids, including illicitly produced fentanyl, since 2013. However, it is worth noting that the prevalence of opioid use disorder has exhibited a reasonably consistent pattern, as reported by the US Department of Health and Human Services (2018). Dowell et al. (2017) presented evidence suggesting that the illicit production of fentanyl, a highly potent opioid, is responsible for the current surge in opioid overdose fatalities.

In addition, opioid overdose fatality rates in the United States experienced a threefold increase between 1999 and 2017. According to Hedegaard et al. (2018), opioid overdoses constituted the predominant factor in the 70,237 fatal drug overdoses that occurred in the United States in 2017. Over time, the opioid epidemic in the United

States has undergone a transformation. Dasgupta et al. (2018) reported that in the early 1980s, the primary use of opioids was for managing acute pain, and the misuse of opioids for nonmedical purposes accounted for a significant proportion of drug-related fatalities. After 10 years, the act of prescribing opioids to manage chronic pain became more popular due to the perception of inadequate treatment. By the year 2000, this pattern had gained momentum following the removal of widely used prescription nonopioid analgesics because of their cardiovascular hazards and concerns regarding acetaminophen toxicity. Around 2010, the incidence of combined opioid analgesic and heroin use increased. During the latter part of the 2010s, there was a growing prevalence of counterfeit medicines and street medications containing highly strong substances, including fentanyl and its analogs.

Many recognized the opioid crisis in the US as one of the worst public health catastrophes of our time before the COVID-19 epidemic took center stage in the media (Darolia & Heflin, 2023). In 2019, the number of Americans who died from opioid overdoses was close to 50,000, which is approximately six times the numbers that perished in 2000. In 2020, the number of deaths attributable to opioids rose by more than 40% from the year before, to almost 69,000. The death toll rose by a further 20% in 2021, approaching 81,000. Overworked health systems and isolation caused by the COVID-19 pandemic likely contributed to the rise in opioid overdoses. Furthermore, the COVID-19 and opioid crises strained the same public health, social service, and educational sectors (Heflin, 2023). This research will facilitate an understanding of the opioid crisis's effects in various societal and community domains, including education, household formation, child welfare, labor markets, housing security, food security, and public budgets. Many of these subjects are currently under-researched.

According to Heflin (2023), there are methodological challenges in this area, but we also draw attention to several crucial insights. First, opioid addiction is a serious health issue that affects many individuals. It is imperative that comprehensive policies consider the needs of the whole person. For example, individuals suffering from opioid use disorders might require food and housing, which reduces the efficacy of treatment plans. Opioid-related policies should fulfill their needs holistically, even though their opioid-related health issues require considerable attention.

Second, as parents, caregivers, employees, and members of families and communities, people with opioid use disorders play significant roles in society. The use of opioids can devastate multigenerational families. Additionally, the use of opioids can negatively impact our educational system, strain social services such as child welfare, increase food insecurity, and decrease productivity, leading to financial costs that surpass the direct effects observed at the local and state levels. This implies the need for comprehensive and far-reaching solutions. Multiple studies (Birnbaum et al., 2006; Birnbaum et al., 2011; Rice et al., 2014) have evaluated the economic consequences of opioid use disorder and fatal opioid overdose. Prescription opioids have been the primary focus of existing research. To provide an example, Florence et al. (2016) estimated that the financial impact of prescription opioid use disorder and fatal overdoses in 2013 amounted to \$78.5 billion (Florence et al., 2016). This estimation covers the components of healthcare, criminal justice, and economic decline. The President's Council of Economic Advisers (CEA) published a report in 2017 highlighting the shortcomings of the Florence et al. study's methodology, which failed to fully assess the societal consequences of fatal overdoses. To evaluate these expenses, CEA incorporated the notion of "willingness to pay" for reductions in mortality risk, referred to as the value of a statistical life (VSL). The CEA study expanded the valuation of opioid use disorder and opioid overdose cases, yielding an estimated economic impact of \$500 billion for 2015. Therefore, this study contributes differently by investigating the link between opioid addiction deaths and socioeconomic factors that incorporate US economic growth.

Review of related studies

The number of outpatient opioid analgesic prescriptions fell by 13% nationally between 2012 and 2015 (FDA, 2017), with more notable declines noted in other areas. This means that the death rate from prescription opioid overdoses has not decreased. However, the country's overdose death rate increased noticeably by 38% during the same period (CDCP, 2017). Prescription opioid overdose deaths have not fallen directly in line with their availability. The county-level correlations between dispensed volume and overdose are weaker than those at the national level (Kertesz, 2017; Dasgupta et al., 2006). Different ideas have been put forward to explain the different death rates linked to synthetic opioids, the possible effects of changing how autopsies are performed, the existence of time-lag effects, and the fact that some therapies are not working (Dasgupta et al., 2013; Alexandridis et al., 2017). It is reasonable to link structural elements like poverty, few chances, unpleasant living and working circumstances, and ill health. This article does not attempt to provide a thorough examination of the underlying causes of overdose, addiction, and pain. It is important to recognize that, while increased opioid availability may have contributed to the increase in overdose incidents, concentrating only on the supply of opioids undermines the effectiveness of treatments (McCaig, 1996; Cicero et al., 2017). The "reversal of fortunes" in life expectancy became a national phenomenon very quickly. While this tendency was first noted by researchers in Appalachia and the Southwest in 2000, by 2015 it had expanded outside of these regions (Masters et al., 2017; Case & Deaton, 2017).

Socioeconomic variables associated with racial/ethnicity, metabolic and behavioral risk, and health care access have made a substantial difference in life expectancy between the most and least healthy counties over the last 20 years (Dwyer-Lindgren et al., 2016). The indicators mentioned above, including a significant increase in income inequality over several decades and the incidence of economic shocks due to deindustrialization and reductions to social safety nets, provide the most recent evidence of a persistent decline tendency. Both physical and mental health have suffered because of the 2008 financial crisis, austerity programs, and other neoliberal policies (Ruckert & Labonté, 2017).

Substance abuse and poverty, in their worst incarnations, interact more strongly when there are mental health issues and unstable living circumstances. The highest pay goes to economically exploited groups in manufacturing and service jobs that carry a high level of physical danger, such as military service. Long-term work-related injuries can cause chronic pain, which can initiate a cycle of infirmity and poverty. While opioid analgesics may help those who are unable to work stay employed, it seems that manual laborers are more likely to use them for nonmedical purposes (Rigg & Monnat, 2015). Overdose rates are highest in the lowest social capital counties throughout a large portion of the nation (Zoorob & Salemi, 2017).

A set of circumstances known as socioeconomic marginalization leads to vulnerability and exclusion from social and economic opportunities. The above-described situations include some elements that cause people to be excluded from the workforce, to use illicit or unofficial means of generating money (such as stealing, drug dealing, or street labor), to have inadequate income, to be in jail or social isolation, to have low socioeconomic status or poverty, and to experience material insecurity (such as unstable housing or food). Drug-related deaths are more common in certain drug user groups than in others. Among these groups are people who are homeless (Fischer et al., 2004), those recently released from prison (Green et al., 2012), those eligible for US Medicaid (a proxy indicator of poverty), the Indigenous (Jongbloed et al., 2014), and the low-income households raised by them (Ho, 2017; Lanier et al., 2012; Silva et al., 2012).

Nevertheless, these features fall short of fully capturing the range of socioeconomic factors that affect the health and risk of overdose among opioid users. Not being able to work (Richardson et al., 2015), making illegal and

unethical money (Ti et al., 2014), managing income assistance payments poorly (Krebs et al., 2016; Otterstatter et al., 2016; Zlotorzynska et al., 2014), and not having enough money (Ompad et al., 2011) are some of the factors that contribute to this trend. However, these factors have not received enough attention in the field of overdose studies (Brunner and Marmot, 2006). Brunner and Marmot (2006) proposed that these factors, in addition to direct material deprivation, influence health outcomes through psychological and behavioral pathways. Brunner and Marmot (2006) assert that persistent stress resulting from devaluation, social exclusion, and inequality can trigger stress reactions, escalating interpersonal conflict, and negatively affecting health. This maintains the power relationships that created these conditions. Both individual overdose and drug-related death are structurally linked to marginalization, which includes restricted access to resources and elements that contribute to drug-related harm, such as income disparity and neighborhood impoverishment. Distribution and management of socioeconomic resources play a mediating role in this relationship (Krebs et al., 2016; Lanier et al., 2012; Otterstatter et al., 2016; Xiang et al., 2012; Zlotorzynska et al., 2014).

It is challenging to identify the underlying reasons for these interactions due to the convergence of various elements. Nonetheless, the correlations between these disorders and their impact on overdose serve as an illustration of the various forms of disadvantage—such as cumulative and spatial life course disadvantage—that, when combined, contribute to health disparities among opioid users. Therefore, to close the gap left by earlier research, this study examines the relationship between opioid addiction deaths and socioeconomic factors that incorporate US economic growth.

Methodology

A cross-sectional dataset was collected from the 2023 record of NCDAS: National Center for Drug Abuse Statistics (Opioid Addiction Statistics) data via the link: [Opioid Crisis Statistics \[2023\]: Prescription Opioid Abuse \(drugabusestatistics.org\)](https://www.drugabusestatistics.org/) in 51 states of America, and the US Census Bureau indicators for socio-economic and economic growth in the United States of America. This study adopted a quantitative research design using quantitative methods such as descriptive statistics, FMOLS, and the OLS regression model for the analysis of the cross-sectional data. The model specification will take the following form:

$$OAD_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1(POV)_i + \beta_2(UNEMP)_i + \beta_3(EDUA)_i + \beta_4(ECG)_i + \mu_i \quad (1)$$

Opioid addiction death (OAD) is the dependent variable, while the independent variable includes unemployment (UNEMP), educational attainment (EDUA) for residents with a bachelor's degree or higher degrees and the economic growth (ECG) measured with the GDP by states in the United States. In addition, poverty, unemployment rate, educational attainment, and economic growth are the socioeconomic factors considered for this study. where i is the cross-section of the 51 American states, β_0 is the constant term, β_1 to β_4 are the coefficient estimates of the independent variables, and μ_i is the error term or residuals.

Phillips and Hansen (Olofin et al., 2019) developed the Fully Modified Least Square (FMOLS) method to administer an optimal co-integrating regression estimation. However, for the co-integration regression, the study used the Pedroni heterogeneous FMOLS estimator because it has the advantage of correcting serial correlation (Rahman et al., 2021). Considering the cross-sectional FMOLS estimator for the coefficient β :

$$\beta^* - \beta = \left(\sum_{i=1}^N L_{22i}^{-2} \sum_{i=1}^T (\chi_i - \bar{\chi}_i)^2 \right) \sum_{i=1}^N L_{11i}^{-1} L_{22i}^{-2} \left(\sum_{i=1}^T (\chi_i - \bar{\chi}_i) \mu_i^* - T \hat{\gamma}_i \right) \quad (2)$$

Where μ_i^* is illustrated below as

$$\mu_i^* = \mu_t - \frac{\hat{L}_{21i}}{\hat{L}_{22i}} \Delta \chi_t, \hat{\gamma}_i = \hat{\Gamma}_{21i} \hat{\Omega}_{21i}^0 - \frac{\hat{L}_{21i}}{\hat{L}_{22i}} (\hat{\Gamma}_{22i} + \hat{\Omega}_{22i}^0)$$

And $\hat{L}_i$ was the lower triangulation of $\hat{\Omega}_i$.

The long-term effects of independent variables on a dependent variable were examined using FMOLS (Rahman et al., 2021). The OLS regression model aids in establishing a connection between the study's relevant variables. We also performed diagnostic tests such as multicollinearity, residual normality, autocorrelation, heteroscedasticity, and model stability to confirm the accuracy and dependability of the model. We used EViews software version 10 for the analysis of this study.

Table 1: Variable measurements

Variables	Measurement	Sources
Opioid addiction deaths	Deaths per 100,000	Opioid Crisis Statistics [2023]: Prescription opioid Abuse (drugabusestatistics.org)
Poverty	Percentage	Poverty in the United States: 2022 (census.gov)
Unemployment	Percentage	Unemployment Rates for States (bls.gov)
Educational attainment	Percentage	S1501: EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT: Census Bureau Table
Economic growth	Millions of US Dollars	Gross Domestic Product by State and Personal Income by State, 4th Quarter 2023 and Preliminary 2023 U.S. Bureau of Economic Analysis (BEA)

Source: Author's computation

Results

Table 2: Descriptive statistics

	OPIOID ADDICTION	POVERTY	UNEMPLOYMENT	EDUCATION ATTAINMENT	ECONOMIC GROWTH
Mean	15.79608	12.59529	3.539216	34.79157	533556.0
Median	15.10000	12.36000	3.400000	34.45000	309601.0
Maximum	42.40000	19.58000	5.300000	63.05000	3862171.
Minimum	3.400000	7.420000	2.000000	24.12000	43130.00
Std. Dev.	9.996719	2.718346	0.826336	7.032941	692205.0
Observations	51	51	51	51	51

Source: Author's computation

Table 2 shows that the average opioid addiction death rate across the 51 American states in 2023 is about 15.8 out of every 100,000 residents that die from opioid addiction, with a variability of about 10 opioid deaths per 100,000; the average poverty rate is about 13% with a variability of about 3%; the average unemployment rate is about 4% across the 51 states with a variability of about 1%; the average educational attainment for the residents with a bachelor's degree or higher is about 35% with a variability of about 7%; and the average economic growth across the 51 states is about 534 million US dollars.

Table 3: Fully Modified Least Squares (FMOLS)

OPIOID ADDICTION	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
POVERTY	0.364883	0.455340	0.801342	0.4271
UNEMPLOYMENT	2.430877	1.434195	1.694942	0.0970
EDUCATION ATTAINMENT	0.646537	0.167786	3.853329	0.0004
ECONOMIC GROWTH	-3.33E-06	1.62E-06	-2.054043	0.0458
C	-17.98043	9.695295	-1.854552	0.0702
R-squared	0.240572			
Adjusted R-squared	0.173068			
S.E. of regression	9.130073			
Long-run variance	54.31615			

Source:

Author's

computation

Table 3 shows that socio-economic factors like unemployment and educational attainment for residents with a bachelor's degree or higher have a positive significant impact at 10% and 5% significance level, respectively, on opioid addiction deaths, while economic growth has a negative significant influence at 5% significance level on opioid addiction deaths in the long run, indicating that in the long run, a high level of economic growth will reduce opioid addiction deaths, while an increase in unemployment and education attainment will contribute to a surge in opioid addiction deaths. This bolstered the concept of socioeconomic marginalization, a set of conditions that cause vulnerability and exclusion from social and economic possibilities. Exclusion from the workforce; unofficial or illicit ways of making money (such as stealing, selling drugs, or working on the streets); material instability (such as unsteady housing or food); inadequate income; social stigma or isolation; and low socioeconomic level or poverty are some of these conditions. As demonstrated by the increased risk of drug-related deaths in specific drug user groups, such as those who are homeless (Fischer et al., 2004), just released from prison (Green et al., 2012), and raised in low-income households (Ho, 2017; Lanier et al., 2012; Silva et al.), social and economic marginalization may be a factor in overdose deaths. These elements, however, fall short of capturing the whole spectrum of socioeconomic influences on the health and danger of opioid overdose. Among these drivers are exclusion from the labor market (Richardson et al., 2015), involvement in the generation of illegal and informal revenue (Ti et al., 2014), and coordinated management of income assistance payments (Krebs et al., 2016; Otterstatter et al., 2016; Zlotorzynska et al., 2014).

Table 4: OLS Regression model

OPIOID ADDICTION	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.	VIF
C	-17.92041	11.87762	-1.508755	0.1382	NA
POVERTY	0.234409	0.550456	0.425844	0.6722	1.372734
UNEMPLOYMENT	3.019066	1.742794	1.732314	0.0899	1.271560
EDUCATION ATTAINMENT	0.629307	0.205266	3.065813	0.0036	1.277731
ECONOMIC GROWTH	-3.40E-06	1.99E-06	-1.713417	0.0934	1.158739
R-squared	0.249222				
Adjusted R-squared	0.183937				
S.E. of regression	9.030658				
Sum squared resid	3751.428				
Log likelihood	-181.9666				
F-statistic	3.817440				
Prob(F-statistic)	0.009224				

Table 4 shows that the overall OLS regression model ($P = 0.009 < 0.05$) implies that the fitted OLS regression model is statistically significant at the 5% level, indicating that opioid addiction deaths are significantly linked to socioeconomic factors like poverty, unemployment, education attainment, and economic growth. The coefficient estimate of socioeconomic factors like unemployment and education attainment has a significant positive influence at 10% and 5% significance level, respectively, on opioid addiction deaths, while the economic growth of the United States negatively influences opioid addiction deaths at 10% significance level, indicating that high levels of unemployment and education attainment for residents with bachelor's degrees and other higher degrees contribute to higher opioid addiction deaths, while high levels of economic growth mitigate opioid addiction deaths. Meanwhile, the variance inflation factors for all the independent variables are less than 5, which suggests that the fitted OLS regression model does not have the problem of multicollinearity, indicating that the model results are reliable.

Figure 1 shows the distribution of opioid addiction deaths in the 51 American states under review. West Virginia demonstrated the highest opioid addiction deaths among the United States.

Opioid Addiction Deaths

Figure 1: Opioid addiction deaths in 51 American states

Diagnostic

checks

Table 5: Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:

F-statistic	1.211831	Prob. F(2,44)	0.3074
Obs*R-squared	2.662581	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.2641

Table 6: Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

F-statistic	1.644000	Prob. F(4,46)	0.1794
Obs*R-squared	6.378879	Prob. Chi-Square(4)	0.1726
Scaled explained SS	4.961656	Prob. Chi-Square(4)	0.2913

Table 5 shows that $P = 0.2641 > 0.05$, which implies that we cannot reject the null hypothesis, indicating that the residuals are not serially correlated. This implies that the model does not suffer from the problem of autocorrelation. Similarly, Table 6 demonstrates that $P = 0.1726 > 0.05$, confirming the absence of heteroscedasticity in the fitted OLS regression model. This also satisfies the OLS assumptions.

Figure 2 shows the normality test using the Jarque-Bera, revealing that $P = 0.1764 > 0.05$, indicating that the residuals are normally distributed, satisfying the OLS normality assumption. Figure 3 shows that the model parameter in the blue line falls between the two 95% confidence intervals (in red), indicating that the fitted OLS regression model parameters are stable.

Figure 2: Normality test

Figure 3: CUSUM Test for the Model Stability Check

Conclusion

Researchers worldwide have extensively studied opioid addiction deaths that occur as a result of drug usage, such as overdose or addiction instances, in developed economies. To date, there has been a lack of research examining the role of economic growth as a socioeconomic factor in the opioid addiction mortality issue within the United States. Hence, this research aims to address the current knowledge gap by examining the relationship between socioeconomic indicators, including poverty, unemployment, educational attainment among individuals with bachelor's degrees and higher degrees, and economic growth.

The findings of the analysis indicate a statistically significant correlation between opioid addiction fatalities and socioeconomic parameters, specifically economic growth. The findings of the FMOLS indicate that conventional socioeconomic factors, such as unemployment and education attainment, have a substantial impact on the prevalence of opioid addiction deaths in the United States. However, the inclusion of economic growth in the analysis demonstrates a significant reduction in opioid addiction deaths within the country. Hence, the socioeconomic consequences of opioid addiction deaths have both positive and negative effects. Consequently, US food and drug authorities should consistently raise awareness among unemployed individuals and those with addiction.

Additionally, the government should implement measures to promote sustainable economic growth and development, which will ultimately reduce opioid addiction deaths in the United States.

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